

Transformation of Australia's vegetated landscapes: the development of VAST-2 (2013)

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Project Objectives

Over the last decade, considerable progress has been made in developing information systems to compile regional scale datasets of the current extent and condition of Australia's vegetation types relative to a pre-European unmodified state. However, little work has been done at a regional level to collate information on the way land use and land management practices have transformed, and continue to transform, the extent and condition of Australia's vegetated landscapes. The absence of a consistent approach to report transformations of native vegetation over space and time remains a source of contention, and even conflict, between those involved in conservation and protection, and those involved in sustainable land use and management. As a result there is no standardized national system to systematically and ecologically account for the transformation of plant communities.

The objectives of this project were to:

- develop a system to integrate information on land use and management and the responses of selected plant communities at sites over time.
- develop a system to provide a consistent national approach for reporting on vegetation transformation, i.e. changes in condition of native plant communities over time.
- develop an approach for consistently describing and collating spatial and temporal patterns and processes associated with the use and management of Australia's vegetated landscapes.
- develop the infrastructure to collate, review and revise a national repository of historical records of changes in land management and their effects on the condition of plant communities and to assess the suitability of this information to inform research priorities.

Methods

Tools were identified and selected for creating a national repository of thematic, mapped, and descriptive information about the transformation of Australia's vegetated landscapes since 1800. This repository was designed to contain multidisciplinary reference material, including historic records from Australian, State and Territory land management agencies, as well as historic national land tenure and land use maps, time-series GIS, remote sensing datasets, surveyors journals, theses, journals and technical reports.

An extensive network of collaborators (land managers, research scientists, and the community) was contacted to provide qualitative and quantitative data about landscape transformation. This information, combined with spatial and temporal information on land use patterns and management regimes produced a simulation of landscape transformation.

Case studies were used to develop and test the system for collecting, collating and analysing historical records of changes in land management and their effects on the condition of plant communities (Figure 1). Qualitative and quantitative data and information were compiled and assigned reliability scores. Condition was consistently scored using three components and 22 indicators, including site regenerative capacity or function (fire effects, soil structure, soil hydrology, soil chemistry, soil biota and reproductive potential), vegetation structure (height, cover and age classes), and species composition (functional groups and species richness) (Figure 2). Tools including wiki-like approaches were investigated to assess whether they offer the benefits of engaging key members of the community and continually growing and improving our knowledge and understanding over time. The repository highlights the quality and quantity of information available.

Figure 1a: Big Scrub (Tintenbar site) showing a healthy closed camphor laurel forest without intervention of land management practices to enable natural regeneration of the indigenous rainforest to proceed.

Figure 1b: Big Scrub (Rocky Creek Dam site) showing a decaying canopy of closed camphor laurel forest after stem injection to kill the overstorey and enable natural regeneration of the indigenous rainforest to proceed.

Methods (continued)

1 Vegetation transformation score
4 Component indices
10 Attribute groups
22 Indicators

Vegetation transformation index

Figure 2: Conceptual hierarchy for assessing the condition of native vegetation at sites comprising 22 indicators, ten attribute groups, three components and one vegetation transformation index for each year of a chronology. Completed graphical results and records were published on the ACEAS data portal.

Major Findings

A system was developed that provided a structure to compile and interpret information gathered in the past about changes in management practices and the effects of these practices on the condition of native plant communities. This process produced a continuous string of information about cause and effect of interventions. The system enabled historical records, starting with explorer's first contact with indigenous peoples and continuing to present day conditions, to be compiled.

Reliability scores provided transparency by accounting for quality of information, published versus unpublished sources. Expert elicitation and multi-criteria analysis enabled collaborators from different disciplines to contribute observational and measurement information. By scoring effects relative to a reference state and treating each indicator equally and independently, changes were able to be scored out of 100%. The indicators were weighted to reflect the knowledge of experienced plant community ecologists—regenerative capacity (55%), vegetation structure (27%) and species composition (18%)—thereby enabling the degree of modification from the reference state to be presented graphically over time (Figure 3).

The system enables land managers and vegetation ecologists to engage and share information equally. Using this system showed that assessing the relative change on vegetation condition need not be a complex task. The system has potential to provide a consistent national approach for reporting on the condition of native vegetation.

Figure 3: Weighted component and total indices for Rocky Creek Dam for the period 1788-2010. Key management practices: A—Indigenous people managing the site, B—Clearing and conversion of rainforest to pasture, C—Start of grazing exotic pastures for dairying, D—Stopped grazing pastures and start of weed incursions, E—Commenced weed removal (Lantana – Privet), F—Commenced monitoring of regeneration, G—Site managed as a high visitor use public reserve.

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science and management?

The new system describes transformation pathways of native vegetation, including positive and negative feedbacks and transitions from one condition state to another, including the replacement, removal or recovery of native vegetation. It offers a robust and flexible approach relevant to Australia's tropical, sub-tropical and temperate bioregions. The visual presentation of the results provides an ecologically meaningful, simple tool for decision makers to track and understand complex ecological processes including degradation, restoration and regeneration.

The system provides a tool for:

- identifying potential risks and barriers to achieving success
- demonstrating progress toward vegetation condition targets
- selecting sites that represent least-cost options for future land use changes.

It also highlights the importance of an accounting system that can be used to track the sustainable use and management of native vegetation across all land use types, and has relevance for managing biodiversity. A wide range of qualitative and quantitative data and information can now be translated, compiled and used to report changes in vegetation condition over time using the new system.

Outputs and products

Vegetation Transformation Study Sites <http://aceas.org.au/portal/>

ACEAS sabbatical project website: http://www.aceas.org.au/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=70&Itemid=74

Thackway, R. and A. Specht (in prep). A system for capturing the effects of land use on vegetation condition.

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